

GENETIC DISORDER AND TREATMENT, PREVENTION FOR THE CONTROL OF GENETIC DISEASES

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Abstract : The article about a genetic disorder is a disease caused in whole or in part by a change in the DNA sequence away from the normal sequence. Genetic disorders can be caused by a mutation in one gene (monogenic disorder), by mutations in multiple genes (multifactorial inheritance disorder), by a combination of gene mutations and environmental factors, or by damage to chromosomes (changes in the number or structure of entire chromosomes, the structures that carry genes).

Key words : mutation , single gene disease , chromosomal disease , multifactorial disease , gynotip , nucleotids , DNA , duplication,

Classification of Genetic diseases:

Single genetic disease mean

When a single mutated gene is known to cause a diseases that is called single gene diseases .Over 4000genetical diseases are caused by it.

Localized small-scale mutations

Mutations of individual genes (e.g sicckle cell anemia ,cystic fibriosis)

Follow classic inheritance patterns (autosomal recessive /dominant ,X-linked)

Chromosomal diseases;

In which genetic diseases a large part of the genetic code is being distruped that is known as chromosomal diseases..Are large-scale mutations of the

chromosomes Excess or deficiency of genes e.g Down syndrome (trisomy 21) .No mutations in individual genes . Duplication or deletion of smaller segments

Multifactorial diseases;

Complex or polygenic diseases are mainly known as multifactorial diseases .This kind of diseases runs in families.Hard to pin down . Majority of diseases have a genetic component . Does not fit inheritance patterns expected in single gene mutations.

WHAT IS GENE ?

Gene is a basic physical unit of heredity which is made up of nucleotides and DNA.Different DNA sequences which are known as genotypes make these genes.

What is Genetic disease ? How does it occur The packaged DNA with all its molecules or all of the genetic material of an organism is known as chromosome and we all know that chromosomes are made of genes

Mainly the abnormality of the chromosomes is known as genetic diseases. Genetic disorders occur when a mutation (a harmful change to a gene also known as a pathogenic variant) affects your genes or when you have the wrong amount of genetic material.

So we can also say the genetic disease is an illness caused by one or more abnormalities in the genome , especially a condition that is present from birth.

Some genetic diseases from this: Hemophilia, Turner syndrome cancer, phenylketonuria ,neurofibromatosis

Turner syndrome

Turner syndrome is one of the most chromosomal diseases in which a female is partly or completely missing an X chromosome . It occurs approximately one in 2000.Short stature ,broad chest ,swollen hands ,low set ears are the symptoms

Neurofibromatosis

Neurofibromatosis is not a single medical disorder but refers to three different conditions involving the development of tumors that may affect brain , spinal cord and the nerves that send signals between the brain and spinal cord and all other parts of the body

Neurofibromatosis type 1 (NF1)

Neurofibromatosis type 2 (NF2)

Schwannomatosis (SWN)

Neurofibromatosis type 1

Neurofibromatosis 1 (NF1) is the most common of the three conditions. Although many people with NF1 inherit the gene that causes the condition, between 30 and 50 percent of cases arise from a spontaneous genetic mutation in the NF1 gene. Once this mutation has occurred, the abnormal gene can be inherited. Each child of an affected parent has a 50% chance of inheriting the gene mutation.

1 in 2700 children have this disease.

Cancer

A hereditary cancer syndrome is a genetic predisposition to certain types of cancer often with onset at an early age caused by inherited pathogenic variants in one or more genes. Most hereditary cancer syndromes exhibit autosomal dominant inheritance. The most common hereditary cancer syndromes related to women's cancer include hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndrome, Lynch syndrome, Li-Fraumeni syndrome, Cowden syndrome, Peutz-Jeghers syndrome and hereditary diffuse gastric cancer.

Cancer is a result of abnormal growth cells. Almost 5-10% of all cancers are hereditary cancer implications genetic.

When the division of cells didn't stay under control it causes cancer. There are many types of cancer but they don't have any general signs and symptoms.

Controllable lifestyle can prevent it.

Hemophilia

This is an inherited genetic disorder which impairs the ability of making blood clots which is the process to stop bleeding. Internal and external bleedings are the general symptoms. There is no cure for it but treatment improves the outcome.

The Odds of having Hemophilia

About 1 in 1600 people will have hemophilia

-1/5000 will be males while 1/1000 will be females

-Hemophilia affect all groups and sexes ,however men will be more prone to get the disorder

This is due to hemophilia being being a recessive X-linked disorder

-It tends to affect males more asthey only need one mutated X chromosome as opposed to famales who need both X chromosome to be mutated

-it may be recessive but it still can happen

-hemophilia is caused by a mutated chromosome

Treatment of genetic diseases

The treatment of genetic diseases is known as gene therapy .This is an ongoing battle with over 1800 completed gene therapy.Some are approved world wide and others are on going .As we saw that almost all kinds of genetic diseases has no way of curation in spite of scientists are trying to bring a tremendous change in Gene therapy

Prevent of genetic disorder

The control of genetic diseases should be based on an integrated and comprehensive strategy combining *best possible treatment* and *prevention* through community education, population screening, genetic counselling and the availability of early diagnosis. Genetic services that are introduced for the control of genetic diseases should provide a strong platform for the application of genetic technology to a broader range of public health challenges.

The future of Medical Genetics

The ever expanding database of human genetic variation and our understanding of genomics will inevitably lead to extensive discovery and development in public health and the availability of tools in the practice of medicine

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Genomics and world health: report of the Advisory Committee on Health Research. Geneva, World Health Organization, 2002.